

STATUS OF SCHOOL LIBRARIES IN INDIA**Dr. Ashwini Anand Vaishnav,**

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ABSTRACT

(The paper defines education, its objectives. Gives role & need of library in school. Analysed and presented statistical data collected from various government reports about schools, school library & librarian in India, Maharashtra and Marathwada. The Paper is concluded with the words that 100% schools do not have libraries, while negligible schools have appointed librarian, even though it is most important component for development of future citizens.)

1. INTRODUCTION

Basic education up to matriculation is essential for every individual. At present aim of education has changed. A child is no longer merely expected to learn the 3R's but he should be aware of his surroundings, know about the events which are taking place, understand the society in which he lives and so on. According to Secondary Education Commission (India. Ministry of Education (1952), p.17-20) and Veer (2010, p.164) objectives of school education are to develop students Culturally, Spiritually, By Character, Physically, psychologically and mentally; Their personality, Education for leadership, Improvement of vocational efficiency, foster sense of true patriotism; i.e. to inculcate a deep love for one's own country.

Through education we are developing future well informed citizens so that they will be able to know their rights and duties, which will help them in development of society. Productive contribution and development of democracy depend on acceptable education as well as on free and unlimited access to thought, culture and information.

Government of India introduced Sarva Shiksha Abiyan (SSA) in 2001. The article 21-A of Constitution of India has made education as a fundamental right, by article 45 of the constitution of India and Right to education Act, 2009 state governments are responsible to provide free and compulsory education for the children up to 14 years of age, with all facilities required including library.

1.1 Role of School Libraries

IFLA/UNESCO School Library Manifesto, (1999) updated in 2013; states that school library is an

important element for providing information to the students as well as develop life-long learning skills amongst them, which helps them to be an enlightened, responsible citizen. School library also plays an important role in developing reading habit amongst students.

Dr. S.R. Ranganathan (1973 p. 61-63) has found four aspects behind the necessity for setting up school libraries. From the angle of education these aspects are:- (i) Beginnings of universal education; (ii) Equality; (iii) Sociological pressure; and (iv) Inevitability of mass teaching. Adding to these ideas, it is to be said that the school library, if properly organised, can make a sound educational base for any individual. (Singh, 1998). Library is the heart of the school and it should be hub of all school activities and the librarian should be a guide philosopher and friend of all its inhabitants. (Ranganathan, 1973; Lahiri, 1994).

While describing place of library in school education Secondary Education Commission (India. Ministry of Education, (1952, p 89-97) opined that, i. schools should have well equipped school library which is being used by students as well as teachers; ii. For every school library there should be professionally trained school librarian.

2. NEED FOR THE STUDY

School Libraries are essential to the development of information literacy, teaching, learning and culture, can cater to the curricular, co-curricular, hobby, recreational and other general information needs of the students and faculty members, can play important role in helping educational system to achieve its goals. It can be made a hub of activities going on in a school. Students can use it for education, information, recreation, inspiration, etc. The performance of students can be improved considerably if they use library regularly. This will greatly help in raising the standard of education. Education being life long process, School Library serves as a stepping stone in this direction. Which shows that School Library, if properly organized, can make a sound basic foundation for the schools in digital environment, will function as an integral part of educational process and act as laboratory for students so as to develop budding citizens.

The prevailing picture of school libraries in India is contrastingly different. A lot needs to be done in order to provide our schools with well organized libraries. In many schools there is no library and where ever there is library it is underdeveloped. There are very few books found in most of these libraries and usually books are kept under lock and key in the Cupboards and Almirahs, without any standards and guidelines, which is defeating whole purpose of school libraries. In spite of this government of India as well as all state governments including Maharashtra are silent about the standards or guidelines for libraries of the government, private aided and private unaided schools affiliated to State Boards. Considering these facts attempt has been made to study the status of schools and school libraries in India.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was undertaken with a view to:

- a. Find out number of schools having library facility;
- b. Ascertain number of schools with school librarian

4. SCOPE

Scope of the study is limited to schools affiliated to State Board, CBSE Board and ICSE Council in India.

5. METHODOLOGY

For present study survey method, especially documentary survey was adopted. Government reports for relevant statistical data were scanned. The data was collected from UDISE+ 2018-19 (Provisional), UDISE 2015-16 and 2016-17 Flash Statistics, Maharashtra Government Resolutions etc.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Data was analysed by using fixed variable viz.

- ❖ For Schools with School Library
 - Total schools with library facility;
 - Board of examination;
 - Management;
 - Category;
 - Location i.e. Rural/Urban.
- ❖ For Schools with School Librarian
 - Total schools with the librarian;
 - Management;
 - Category

6.1 SCHOOLS WITH SCHOOL LIBRARY

The school library is integral to the educational process. Encouraged at the right age, the children are sure to develop a love for books. –Catch them Young is therefore the motto of school libraries. (Mahajan, 2010).

According to Dr. S. R. Ranganathan (1973, p.108) to train students in use of externalized memory; individual instruction; varying the field of study with the individual; and learning by each at his own speed; for an active, global, experimental, creative, and socializing process of education require library work at school library.

6.1.1 Total Number of Schools and School Libraries

In India by the year 2018-19 there are in all 1550006 schools including Government schools, Madarshas, Unrecognised, private schools managed by trusts, political, religious/charitable organizations. In Maharashtra State there are in all 109942 schools, while Marathwada has in all 22259 schools. The data presented in table 1.1 shows that 100% schools in India, Maharashtra or Marathwada do not have library facility, which is contradictory to the provisions under Right to Education Act, 2009.(India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy. (2020); Right to Education Act, 2009)

Table 1.1: Total number of Schools

	Total no. of Schools	Schools with Library facility	Percentage of schools with Library Facility
India	1550006	955797	61.66
Maharashtra	109942	89545	94.89
Marathwada	22259	16496	74.11

The data was further collected and analysed for the percentage of schools having library facility in India, Maharashtra as well as in Marathwada as shown in Figure 1.1. The data about schools with library facility in Marathwada was not available for the years 2014-15 and 2015-16. It can be noted from the Figure 1.1 that Percentage of schools having library facility in India, Maharashtra as well as in Marathwada is decreasing every year. To impart quality education to school pupil we must provide certain minimum facilities in the school to create a pleasant atmosphere for the children to study in. Therefore every school should have library.(India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of Education, 1986). The government authorities seem to unconcerned about schools having library facility.

Maharashtra state has six administrative divisions, one of them is Aurangabad division, popularly known as Marathwada. Marathwada consists of eight districts viz. Aurangabad, Beed, Hingoli, Jalna, Latur, Nanded, Osmanad and Parbhani.

As per latest UDISE+ report 2018-19 (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy, 2020). there are in all 22259 schools in Marathwada, which cover ICSE, CBSE, Religious schools as well as state board- government, private aided and private unaided, schools run by tribal/social welfare department (Ashramshala), unrecognised schools, etc. The district wise distribution of schools along with library facility in Marathwada is shown in Figure 1.2. Figure 1.2 indicates that in no district 100% schools are having library facility, while every school need to have its library. (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of Education, 1986).

6.1.2 Schools with Library by Board of Examination

There are mainly three types of boards conducting school education in India. The first is Indian Certificate of Secondary Education (ICSE) Council, the second Central Board School Examination (CBSE) both are coordinated at national level and conduct the examination at 10th (after high school) level in the schools affiliated to them. All CBSE schools follow textbooks written and published by the NCERT. e.g. Central schools named Kendriya Vidyalaya. After completion of 10 years of schooling State Board Conducts the examination.

The data collected has been presented in table 2.1. total schools with library facility while table 2.2 presents district wise distribution of schools by Board of examination.

It can be noted from the table 2.1 and 2.2 that 100% CBSE and ICSE schools have provided library facility since provision of library facility is precondition for getting recognition by CBSE and ICSE Board. While Of the State Board schools only 61.03% in India, 81.23% in Maharashtra and 73.95% from Marathwada provided library facility. As regards districtwise distribution of school with library facility it can be noted that 73.53%, 57.34%, 77.11%, 69.58%, 86.06%, 73.08%, 87.09% and 81.02%

State Board schools respectively from Aurangabad, Beed, Hingoli, Jalana, Latur, Nanded, Osmanabad and Parbhani provided library facility. Which is a sorry state of affair for state board schools when Library is considered as educational hub as well as heart of school education.

Table 2.1 : Schools with School Libraries by Board of Examination

Board of Examination	India		Maharashtra		Marathwada	
	Total Schools	Schools with Library	Total Schools	Schools with Library	Total Schools	Schools with Library
CBSE	22746	22746	1028	1028	128	128
ICSE	2569	2569	250	250	06	06
State Board	1524691	930482	108664	88267	22125	16362
Total	1550006	955797	109942	89545	22259	16496

Table 2.2 : Schools in Marathwada by Board of Examination: Districtwise Distribution

Board of Examination	Aurangabad	Beed	Hingoli	Jalna	Latur	Nanded	Osmanabad	Parbhani	Total
CBSE	46 (46)	15 (15)	04 (04)	15 (15)	18 (18)	14 (14)	06 (06)	10 (10)	128 (128)
ICSE	03 (03)	01 (01)	00 (00)	01 (01)	01 (01)	00 (00)	00 (00)	00 (00)	06 (06)
State Board	4363 (3208)	3692 (2117)	1311 (1011)	2433 (1693)	2697 (2321)	3715 (2715)	1836 (1599)	2097 (1699)	22125 (16362)
Total	4412 (3257)	3708 (2133)	1315 (1015)	2449 (1709)	2697 (2340)	3729 (2729)	1842 (1605)	2107 (1709)	22259 (16496)

6.1.3 Schools with Library facility by Management

School authorities or governing bodies are Govt. of India (Central Schools), State governments through department of education, Local bodies (such as Zilla Parishad, Panchayat Samiti, Cantonment Board, Municipal bodies, Corporations, etc.), Private bodies- Private aided and unaided, individuals and other public sector undertakings, religious schools etc.

Each state has three kinds of schools that follow state curriculum. The government schools are run by government in its own land and buildings, payment of its staff is also made from government resources. The fees of these schools is minimal. In *Private Unaided Schools* as the name suggest they do not get

government grants, hence fees charged to students is very high, the management has to pay salary of their teachers. The third type of schools are grant in aid schools to which government gives the grant. These schools are owned by a private agency in their own land and building. The grant-in-aid is meant to help to reduce the fees and make it possible for poor families to send their children. Salary of staff of these schools is paid by the state government and fees is also minimal like government schools. In Maharashtra there are government schools run by Maharashtra government through department of education. A few schools are run by the Government of India. However, a large number are run by private bodies or individuals. Having given the responsibility of development of primary and higher/secondary education, government is committed to provide quality of education for all children. (Right of children to free and compulsory education act, 2009).

Table 3.1 Schools with Library facility by Management

Governing Body	Percentage of Schools with Library Facility		
	India	Maharashtra	Marathwada
Government	85.47	79.08	70.43
Private Aided	86.58	86.63	81.54
Private Unaided	78.26	83.87	76.86
Others	47.61	68.06	56.72

Table 3.2 Schools with Library facility in Marathwada by Management: Districtwise Distribution

District/Management	Government	Private Aided	Private Unaided	Others
Aurangabad	2170 1465(67.51%)	950 808(85.05%)	1277 977(76.51%)	15 07(46.67%)
Beed	2549 1344(52.73%)	740 534(72.16%)	414 251(60.63%)	05 04(80.00%)
Hingoli	888 696(78.38%)	208 161(77.40%)	214 156(72.90%)	05 02(40.00%)
Jalana	1557 1032(66.28%)	370 304(82.16%)	509 364(71.51%)	13 08(61.54%)
Latur	1309 1109(84.72%)	934 830(88.87%)	451 400(88.67%)	03 01(33.33%)
Nanded	2259 1621(71.56%)	942 696(73.89%)	514 402(78.21%)	14 10(71.43%)
Osmanabad	1120 965(86.16%)	463 421(90.93%)	252 215(85.32%)	07 04(80.00%)
Parbhani	1150 925(80.43%)	473 388(77.80%)	479 394(82.25%)	05 02(40.00%)
Total	13002 9157(70.43%)	5080 4142(81.54%)	4110 3159(76.86%)	67 38(56.72%)

Attempt has been made to collect the data for schools and schools with library facility by Governing Body in India, Maharashtra and Marathwada. The analysed data is shown in table 3.1. The Table 3.1 shows that more number of Private Aided schools have library facility than Government, Private unaided or schools by other Management. The data was further analysed by management of schools in each district of Marathwada, which is presented in table 3.2. It can be noted from table 3.2 that except Nanded district more number of Private aided schools have library facility than Government, Private unaided or schools by other Management.

6.1.4 Schools with Library facility by Location

Table 4.1: Schools with Library facility by Location

Location	India	Maharashtra	Marathwada
Rural	1304063 779356(60.09%)	84140 67859(80.22%)	17499 12789(73.08%)
Urban	245943 176441(73.97%)	25802 21686(84.28%)	4760 3707(77.88%)

Table 4.2 Schools with Library facility in Marathwada by Location: Districtwise Distribution

District	Rural	Urban
Aurangabad	3248 2335(71.89%)	1164 922(79.21%)
Beed	3189 1832(57.45%)	519 301(58.00%)
Hingoli	1128 881(78.10%)	187 134(71.66%)
Jalana	2027 1399(69.02%)	422 309(73.72%)
Latur	1945 1666(85.66%)	752 674(89.63%)
Nanded	2949 2151(72.94%)	780 578(74.10%)
Osmanabad	1536 1291(87.41%)	571 314(86.02%)
Parbhani	1477 1234(80.34%)	365 475 (83.19%)
Total	17499 12789(73.08%)	4760 3707(77.88%)

By April 2020, India has 28 States and 8 Union Territories. Maharashtra is one of the 28 states. Maharashtra state has six administrative divisions, Aurangabad Division popularly known as Marathwada is one of them. Major part of India, Maharashtra as well as Marathwada is rural and major population resides in rural area. The data was analysed by location of schools with library facility in

India, Maharashtra and Marathwada as shown in table 4.1 while data of schools with library facility was further analysed by location in individual district of Marathwada as presented in table 4.2. The figures in bold indicate total number of schools, while the figures in light indicate total number of schools with library facility and percentage of schools with library facility is given in bracket.

It can be noted from the table 4.1 that more number of Schools in urban area have library facility than their counter part in rural area. It can also be noted from table 4.2 that except Hingoli and Osmanabad in all districts of Marathwada more schools in urban area have library facility than its counter part in rural area. It can be further noted from the table 4.1 and 4.2 that along with majority population, the majority schools in India, Maharashtra as well as in Marathwada are found in rural area, however they lack library facility.

6.1.5 Schools with library facility by Category

At present the school education in India is provided with four categories viz. Primary(Class I-V & age 6-10 years old), Middle or Upper Primary (Class VI-VIII & age 11-14 years old), High School (Class IX-X & age 15-16 years old) and Higher Secondary (IX-XII & age 17 and 18). New Education Policy (NEP), provides Foundation Stage covering Pre-Primary and class 1-2 which covers five years (Age 3-8 years); Preparatory Stage from class 3-5 (Age 8-11); Middle Stage from class 6-8 (Age 11-14) and High Stage from class 9-12 (Age 14-18). (India Ministry of Human Resource Development. Dept. of Higher Education, 2019)

As per the present Govt. of India policy the schools in India in general and Marathwada in particular has four levels: lower primary, upper primary, high and higher secondary schools. The lower primary level schools are divided into five, upper primary school into three, high school into two and higher secondary into two. State government has the responsibility to provide quality education at primary, upper primary, high school and higher secondary level. (Right of children to free and compulsory education act, 2009).

The data for schools with library facility is not available by category of schools with library facility for the year 2017-18 and 2018-19. The present data has been collected from Flash Statistics for the year 2016-17 (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy. 2018), the data was collected for the schools with library by their category which shown in table 5.1. Since the Flash Statistics gives data up to state level only, while district wise data of schools having library facility by category is not available. Hence data for India and Maharashtra only has been presented in the table 5.1. Figures in bracket indicate percentage of schools with library facility during 2016-17.

It can be noted from the table 5.1 that in all in India 82.96% and in Maharashtra 96.74% schools were with library facility. It can be further noted from the table 5.1 that more than 92% schools with Primary,

Upper Primary Secondary and Higher Secondary schools in India as well as schools with Upper Primary, Secondary and Higher Secondary have library facility; while in Maharashtra more than 98% schools with Primary, Upper Primary, Secondary & Higher Secondary; Upper Primary with Secondary and Higher Secondary as well as schools with Primary, Upper Primary and Secondary have library facility.

Table 5.1: Schools with library facility by Category

Category	India	Maharashtra
Primary Only(I-V)	847121(79.84%)	53215(95.46%)
Primary with UP(I-VIII)	287265(87.96%)	29645(96.60%)
Primary, U primary, Sec. & Higher Sec.(I-XII)	48543(94.41%)	5234(98.30%)
U Primary only(VI-VIII)	147579(77.51%)	116(87.07%)
U. Primary with Sec. & H. Sec.(VI-XII)	33586(92.67%)	1409(98.44%)
Primary with U. Primary & Sec.(I-X)	59549(90.70%)	9143(98.25%)
U. Primary with Sec.(VI-X)	50917(90.10%)	6209(97.95%)
Secondary only(IX-X)	33934(79.83%)	1296(91.90%)
Sec. with Higher Sec.(IX-XII)	22560(90.70%)	193(97.41%)
Higher Sec. only/Jr. College(XI-XII)	11436(85.94%)	2253(94.10%)
Total	1535610(82.96%)	108713(96.74%)

6.2 SCHOOLS WITH SCHOOL LIBRARIAN

School librarian is important for a school library. He is inseparable part of curriculum, he is a teacher, he encourages lifelong reading and is responsible for promoting higher test scores and students retention rate. School librarians are expert in helping students to think, create, and grow. (NASSP, February6, 2020); are well versed with technology, keep users honest by teaching them avoiding plagiarism, make school library as an hub of all school activities, create safe space for users, teach pupil 21st century skills, build future citizens (Erin , April 08, 2019), expert in collaboration with teachers, School librarian is most distinctive and the most responsible human constituent of a school library. (Ranganathan, 1973). CILIP (2004) recommends that school librarian work in partnership with key internal and external partners to improve the quality of the school library.

6.2.1 Total Schools with school Librarians

According to available records the percentage of schools with school librarian is shown in table 1.1

(India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy, 2016); (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy, 2018). While the reports for the year 2017-18 and 2018-19 do not provide data about school librarian. It can be noted from Table/Figure 1.1 that number of having librarian are negligible. The Secondary Education Commission recommendations state that “Trained librarians who have love for books and an understanding of students’ interests should be provided in all schools.” To implement this recommendation Government of India, Ministry of Education has asked State government to appoint full time librarian in all schools on equivalent salary scale of teachers. Every school with 500 pupils a full time librarian is suggested. ((India. Ministry of Education , 1952)

Table 1.1 Schools with School Librarian

School Libraries with Librarian\ Year	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
India	16.53%	20.70%	05.02%
Maharashtra	18.46%	19.68%	06.37%

6.2.2 Schools with School Librarian by Management

Data about percentage of schools having school librarian by management was collected from Flash Statistics 2016-17 (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy, 2018). The Report gives management wise data only for national level, hence collected data about schools with librarian by management is about national level only, which is presented in figure 2.1. It can be noted from the figure 2.1 that At all India level more number of Private Unaided schools have Librarian, followed by Private aided schools, however percentage of schools having school librarian is very scanty.

6.2.3 Schools with school Librarian by category

The data was collected by category of schools having school librarian at all India and Maharashtra level from Flash statistics, (India. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Department of School Education and Literacy, 2018), which is presented in Table 3.1/Figure3.1. It can be noted from table 3.1/Figure 3.1 that where ever there are Secondary and Higher Secondary Schools in India as well as in Maharashtra more number of schools have appointed librarian as compared to other categories of the schools. As compared to India position of schools appointing librarian is better in Maharashtra, may be due to Chiplunkar Samit's report.

As per Chiplunkar Samiti's report, Maharashtra Government issued a Government Resolution (GR) dated 28th June, 1994 wherein for the first time the post of school librarian was created in private schools as per the norms given therein. In all 284 full time and 940 part time librarians posts were sanctioned to private aided schools. In 2006 Maharashtra Government issued GR for the private aided schools, which have student's strength more than 1000 and where there is approved part time librarian in such 924 schools the part time librarian will be upgraded as full time librarian. However as per Maharashtra Government GR (September 01, 2018) , the private aided schools have been sanctioned 2409 posts of full time librarian and 2322 posts of part time librarian. As per pay bill of August 2016, there were 1813 full time and 1615 part time librarians are working in the state. This indicates that 596 full time and 707 part time librarians posts are vacant. However as per GR dated 1st September, 2018 the 596 part time librarians will be upgraded as full time librarian as per the norms.

Table 3.1 School with school Librarian by category

Category	India	Maharashtra
Primary Only	1.53	1.54
Primary with UP	4.45	2.94
Primary, U primary, Sec. & Higher Sec.	34.43	34.54
U Primary only	1.32	18.10
U. Primary with Sec. & H. Sec.	20.53	18.17
Primary with U. Primary & Sec.	15.80	15.39
U. Primary with Sec.	5.23	8.05
Secondary only	10.85	13.66
Sec. with Higher Sec.	24.58	20.21
Higher Sec. only/Jr. College	39.84	45.81
Total	5.02	6.37

7 CONCLUSION

The data presented shows that 100% schools in India, Maharashtra as well as in Marathwada do not provide library facility. Percentage of schools having library facility is decreasing every year. Regarding distribution of schools by Board of examination shows that 100% CBSE and ICSE schools have Library facility, while in case of State Board schools failed to do so. The data regarding distribution of schools with library facility by management shows that more number of Private Aided schools provide library

facility, than Government, Private Unaided and schools by Other Managing bodies. Distribution of schools by location shows that even though there are more number of schools in Rural area than urban area, but more number of schools in Urban area provide library facility. Analysis of schools by category shows that more number of elementary schools with Secondary and Higher Secondary Classes have library facility than only Primary, only Upper Primary or only Primary and Upper Primary i.e. Elementary schools, it indicates that that government authorities seem to be unconcerned about State Board Schools having Library facility.

As regards the School Librarian the data shows very negligible percentage of schools have appointed librarian. It is also a clear fact that government authorities are negligent about appointing librarian in State Board schools in India in general and Maharashtra in particular. As compared to India, more number of schools in Maharashtra appointed librarian. This can be the effect of Chiploonkar Samit's Report (1994).

(Author acknowledges with thanks the support from ICSSR under Senior Fellowship Programme)

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